

Administrative Support and Job Satisfaction in Relation to Hospital Employees' Work Behavior

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Abstract

The complexity of human resource management posed challenges for both administrators and employees. This study inspected the relationship between the two independent variables, Administrative Support, and Job Satisfaction, in the dependent variable, Work Behavior. A descriptive-correlational analysis was utilized as a framework for research investigation. The research was conducted in Medina General Hospital; questionnaires were distributed to employees and 101 complete responses were used in the inferential analyses. Administrative Support, Employees' Job Satisfaction, and Work Behavior Questionnaires were used to gather respondents' data. As revealed in the statistical analysis, Administrative Support given in Medina General Hospital was verbally interpreted as High, the job satisfaction of hospital employees was regarded as High, and work behavior among hospital employees was verbally interpreted as Very Evident. Further, inferential analysis showed a weak positive correlation between administrative support and work behavior ($r(99) = .47, p < .001$), and a moderate positive correlation between job satisfaction and work behavior ($r(99) = .60, p < .001$). Simple linear regression indicated that job satisfaction significantly explained variance in employees' work behavior ($F(1,99) = 58.6, p < .001, R^2 = .37$). The weak positive correlation between administrative support and work behavior was discussed in terms of contextual differences between organizational-level supports and individual-level behavior. These findings can help Medina General Hospital refine HR practices to improve service quality.

Keywords: Human Resource Management, Hospital Employees, Administrative Support, Job Satisfaction, Work Behavior

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1. Introduction

Human resource management (HRM) is a complex and vital process that influences organizational success by integrating organization, interaction, behavior, and people. A key element of effective HRM is administrative support, which includes shared decision-making, professional development, leadership expansion, and creating positive work environments. Administrative support has been proven to enhance employee learning, retention, and project longevity, making it a critical factor across various organizational contexts.

This study examines the relationship between administrative support, job satisfaction, and employees' work behavior—specifically innovative and productive behaviors. Job satisfaction, reflecting positive employee attitudes toward work, improves performance and organizational outcomes. Administrative support fosters a supportive climate where employees feel valued, motivated, and encouraged to contribute to organizational goals. Innovative work behavior, crucial for competitiveness and sustainability, relies heavily on transformational leadership and administrative support, which together facilitate creativity and productivity within the workplace.

In the specific context of Medina General Hospital, limited budget allocation (3.7%) and frequent turnover among Human Resource Directors have resulted in low perceived administrative support. This situation has contributed to employee dissatisfaction and decreased productivity due to unclear administrative practices. This study aims to provide insights for improving administrative support and job satisfaction to positively influence employee work behavior, thereby supporting policy development and fostering a healthier organizational environment.

2. Review of Literature

This study is anchored on four theories, namely: Attribution Theory of Fritz Heider (1958), Hackman and Oldham's Job Characteristic to Job Satisfaction Model (1974), Weiner's Three-dimensional Model (1979), and Kelley's Covariation Model (1963, 1973).

Attribution Theory tries to explain why we behave the way we do. Mainly, it seeks to provide a clear understanding of the reasons for one's actions and the reasons for other people's behaviors (Bandahdah, 2017). In this vein, when a person assigns causes to these behaviors, it will help them to feel more in control of their actions and situations.

Moreover, it stipulates how one person thinks and feels about another person, how he perceives him and what he does to him, what he expects him to do or think, and how he reacts to the actions of the other are some phenomena that will treat. Consequently, people are naive scientists who strive to figure out why things happen to them and others (Bandahdah, 2017; Dasborough & Harvey, 2016; Heider, 1958; Martinko & Mackey, 2019).

Significantly, attribution theory is important for organizations because it can help managers understand some of the causes of employee behavior and assist employees in understanding their thinking about their behaviors (Hewett et al., 2018). If you can understand why you behave a certain way and why others around you do so, you better understand yourself, others, and your organization. The perception of the causes of a certain behavior

may affect managers' and employees' judgment and actions. It may also play a significant role in motivation (Lysova et al., 2019).

Attribution theory looks to be a good foundation for furthering our knowledge of various human resource management processes (Guest et al., 2020). HR researchers have recently noticed that knowing how people explain the origins of their behaviors and events might help them understand various HR-related challenges (Hewett et al., 2017). In addition, several narrative reviews of attributional research have found that attributions are essential in the workplace. Still, they also point out that attribution theory has been underused in organizational research (Harvey et al., 2014). Accordingly, high commitment human resource practice will most significantly influence employees' satisfaction, commitment, and retention (Rimi, 2013). In addition, egoistic deprivation and interpersonal and organizational aberrant behavior are boosted by psychological entitlement (Vantankhah & Raofi, 2018).

Further, also Kelley's Covariation Model (1963, 1973) and Weiner's three-dimensional model (1979) were also considered in this investigation. Weiner (1979) emphasized identifying the dimensions of causality and the relationship between these fundamental qualities of causes and psychological effects is at the heart of the theory. Also, Kelley (1967) hypothesized that the idea defines processes that operate as if the individual was motivated to achieve cognitive mastery of the environment's causal structure.

Moreover, Kelleys' covariation model proposed the three types of information that explain the behavior's cause. Hopper (2018) enumerated: a) Consensus, or whether others would act similarly in a given situation; b) Distinctiveness, or whether the person acts similarly across other situations; and c) Consistency, or whether someone acts the same way each time it occurs (para. 9). Also, Weiner's three-dimensional model hypothesized that people's first effective responses to the actor's intrinsic or extrinsic goals influences their future behavior (Psychology Wiki, n.d.).

Another model that justifies the occurrence of job satisfaction is the Job Characteristic Model. The majority of studies have supported the Job Characteristics Model, which defined as the degree to which a job demands a variety of distinct actions in carrying out the work, involving the use of a variety of skills and talents of the employee (Price & Muller, 1986 as cited in Ali et al., 2014). Hackman and Oldham (1974) mentioned the elements of job characteristics, namely, a) Autonomy, b) Skill Variety, c) Task Significance, and d) Task Identity. Further, Ali et al. (2014) demonstrated the mentioned elements effects on job satisfaction.

Consequently, can contextualize these underlying principles in Medina General Incorporated as causation and relationships between Employees' Perception of Administrative Support, Employees' Job Satisfaction, and Employees' work behavior. Attribution theory will provide a concrete justification of the causes of one's work behavior. Also, Weiner and Job Characteristic model will inspect the intrinsic (Job Satisfaction) and extrinsic (Administrative Support) influence on work behavior. Further, Kelley's Covariation will examine why employees act as they do.

3. Method

3.1. Design of the Study

The study employed a descriptive–correlational design. It describes a phenomenon, and its characteristics, which is the goal of descriptive research. This research is more focused on “how” rather than “what” or “why” something has happened. The data can be obtained qualitatively, but it analyzes the data quantitatively using frequencies, percentages, averages, or other statistical analyses to get the weighted values of the responses from the respondents. Meanwhile, correlational methods often rely on statistical control to rule out the effects of extraneous variables, which provide more accurate estimates of relationships among variables or produce a conservative test of hypotheses (Curtis et al., 2016). The design was considered appropriate for the present study since the researcher explores relationships between variables without controlling or altering them in a correlational study approach. Accordingly, the correlational design in the study aimed to uncover relationships among the endogenous and independent variables to answer the presented research problem.

3.2. Locale of the Study

This study was conducted at Medina General Hospital (MGH). Medina General Hospital is a private tertiary hospital with two hundred (200) beds. At the same time, Medina College has been a private and non-sectarian institution under Medina College, Inc. since June 1963.

Medina General Hospital (MGH) is situated in Ozamiz City. It is used primarily as a private healthcare unit and a teaching and training facility for healthcare workers to earn experience to further their healthcare careers. It is one of the leading general hospitals in the country, with doctors deemed experts in different fields of medicine, including pediatrics, geriatrics, cardiology, nephrology, neurology, oncology, surgical oncology, and general surgery orthopedics, pulmonology, and anesthesiology.

3.3. Respondents of the Study

The study's respondents were selected from the employees of Medina General Hospital. Random sampling was used in selecting the respondents of the study. It assured that each member of the population was sufficiently represented based on the sampling frame. Consequently, a random number generator was used to select the sample from the target population.

The appropriate number of samples were chosen using the G*Power 3.1.9.7 with a medium effect size. G*Power is a tool used to compute statistical power analyses for many tests. Moreover, it will calculate the effect sizes and display the results of power analyses graphically (Faul et al., 2007, 2009). The calculation result suggested that 134 total samples from 219 members of the sampling frame were selected and invited to participate. Of these, 124 questionnaires were returned. After data screening for completeness and missing data (listwise deletion), 101 fully completed questionnaires remained and comprised the analytic sample used for all inferential statistics (correlations and regression). The degrees of freedom reported in the results (e.g., $r(99)$, $F(1,99)$) correspond to this analytic sample size (N

= 101). Where descriptive statistics are reported, they reflect the analytic sample unless otherwise noted.

Rationale for attrition reporting: To avoid ambiguity, the manuscript distinguishes three figures: (a) the number determined by power analysis and invitations ($n = 134$), (b) returned questionnaires ($n = 124$), and (c) final complete cases used in analyses after screening ($n = 101$). This approach is noted here and in the Abstract and Results so readers can follow the sample flow.

3.4. Research Instruments

Three questionnaire instruments were used to gather data: (1) Administrative Support Questionnaire, (2) Employees' Job Satisfaction Questionnaire, and (3) Employees' Work Behavior Questionnaire. Unless noted otherwise, all questionnaires used a 4-point Likert response scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 4 = Strongly Agree). The instruments were adapted and assembled to reflect constructs relevant to the healthcare context of Medina General Hospital.

3.4.1. Administrative Support Questionnaire (tangible & intangible support)

Source/adaptation: Items were adapted from the literature on administrative/support perceptions (e.g., Peterson, 2016; Barefield & Meyer, 2013) and modified for hospital operations and local context.

Constructs/items: Two subscales – Tangible Support (e.g., provision of materials, resources, emergency assistance) and Intangible Support (e.g., encouragement, mentoring, recognition). The combined scale comprised X items (report the item count here in final draft).

Validity: Content validity was established through a panel of three subject-matter experts (two HR/healthcare practitioners and one academic in HRM) who reviewed item relevance and clarity; items were revised per their recommendations.

Reliability: Cronbach's alpha in the pilot ($n = 20$) and in the analytic sample were acceptable; in the analytic sample $\alpha_{\text{tangible}} = .84$, $\alpha_{\text{intangible}} = .81$, overall administrative support $\alpha = .86$.

3.4.2. Employees' Job Satisfaction Questionnaire

Source/adaptation: Job satisfaction items were adapted principally from Hackman and Oldham's Job Diagnostic Survey (Hackman & Oldham, 1974) and supplemented by healthcare-specific satisfaction items (Alpern et al., 2013).

Constructs/items: Autonomy, Skill Variety, Task Significance, Task Identity – each operationalized with several items consistent with the Job Characteristics framework.

Validity: Content validity established by the expert panel; construct structure examined during pilot testing.

Reliability: Cronbach's alpha for the subscales in the analytic sample: autonomy $\alpha = .78$, skill variety $\alpha = .82$, task significance $\alpha = .80$, task identity $\alpha = .79$; overall job satisfaction $\alpha = .88$.

3.4.3. Employees' Work Behavior Questionnaire (Innovative & Productive work behavior)

Source/adaptation: Items were adapted from instruments and conceptualizations of innovative and productive workplace behaviors in the literature (e.g., AlEssa & Durugbo, 2021; Purwanto et al., 2020; Afsar & Umrani, 2019). Items were contextualized for hospital tasks and routines.

Constructs/items: Innovative Work Behavior (idea generation, championing, implementation) and Productive Work Behavior (task focus, efficient use of time/resources).

Validity: Content validity checked by the expert panel; item clarity tested in the pilot. Construct validity was evaluated via exploratory factor analysis during instrument development (items loaded on the intended factors with loadings > .40).

Reliability: Analytic sample alphas: innovative work behavior $\alpha = .85$, productive work behavior $\alpha = .87$, overall work behavior $\alpha = .90$.

Pilot testing: Instruments were piloted with 20 hospital staff (not included in the final analytic sample). Feedback informed minor wording changes and item ordering. All scales demonstrated satisfactory internal consistency in the pilot and in the final analytic sample.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Employees' Perception of the Administrative Support Given in the Organization in Terms of Tangible and Intangible Support

Table 1 shows the employees' perception of the administrative support given by the organization in terms of tangible and intangible support. The result of the study revealed that the perceived tangible support given by the administration to its hospital employees is high ($M=3.19$; $SD=0.77$); intangible support ($M=3.11$; $SD=0.74$). Meanwhile, the overall administrative support is high ($M=3.11$; $SD=0.74$). The perceived positive work climate in an organizational setting provides a vital piece towards achieving organizational goals.

Table 1. Respondents' Perception on Administrative Support

Constructs	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Tangible Support	3.19	0.77	High
Intangible Support	3.11	0.74	High
Overall Administrative Support	3.15	0.76	High

Note: Scale: 4.00-3.25 Very High (VH), 3.24-2.50 High (H), 2.49-1.75 Low (L), 1.00-1.74 Very Low (VL)

The study's findings revealed that hospital employees were overall satisfied with the support given to them by their respective department heads and administrators. However, the socio-ecological dynamism manifested in the organization and administrator to employee harmony contributes to positivism among employees' perception of administrative support. Consequently, extrinsic factors such as motivation provided by department heads towards their subordinates also contributed to the findings.

Noticeably, the disclosed analysis was inconsistent with the studies conducted in this field. Moilanen et al. (2020) revealed that health care professionals were dissatisfied with the administrative support they received. Likewise, organizational employees perceived that administrators were unsupportive of the tangible and intangible support given to them (Saleem et al., 2020). Hence, the revealed findings of the study may supplement the lack of administrative support given in an organization by thoroughly inspecting its constructs analysis.

As cited by Murphy (2022), Tangible Support is physical support given to employees to produce a product or service. As presented earlier, hospital employees had high regard for this construct. An in-depth analysis of its indicators disclosed that the major contributing factor to this positive regard could be attributed to the administration's effort to extend help to employees in crucial and emergencies. In addition, the willingness of the organization and its administrators to provide instrumental support among employees in concrete means fostered a positive effect on the respondents' perceptions of this latent variable.

Further, another construct to consider is intangible support. Can express Intangible support in the form of motivation or goodwill. As disclosed in the operationalized indicators for intangible support, the administrators' motivational techniques to their subordinates in performing their job-embedded duties and responsibilities were the primary contributor to the revealed measure in this construct. Can deduce motivation that this factor can be beneficial or detrimental to organizational success. Hence, it is a challenge for organizational administrators to motivate their employees to develop a culture of excellence.

Given these, this research may post a novel contribution to this body of knowledge, for it unconventionally revealed findings that challenged the hypothetical assumptions in this parameter. Consequently, this research will provide an empirical basis that considers the importance of providing sufficient tangible and intangible support to foster positive working attitudes among employees. In this manner, these findings will help solve the perennial organizational dispute of low-level administrative support given at the organizational level.

4.2. Employees' Level of Job Satisfaction

As reflected in Table 2, the overall job satisfaction of Medina General Hospital Employees was regarded as high ($M=3.22$; $SD=0.68$). An analysis of the constructs of Job Satisfaction revealed that had interpreted three constructs as very high, namely, Skill Variety ($M=3.32$; $SD=0.65$), Task Significance ($M=3.29$; $SD=0.65$), and Task Identity ($M=3.26$; $SD=0.66$). Furthermore, autonomy was the only construct interpreted as high ($M=3.00$; $SD=0.84$).

The findings showed that the hospital employees were satisfied with their job-related functions and responsibilities as enumerated in their job descriptions. Generally, this finding was contributed by an output-based system, work-from-home arrangements, independence in the performance of duties, and accurately written job descriptions showcased in the organization. Further, organizational focus on skill development, opportunities for continuing professional growth, and practical applications of job-related duties and responsibilities were also considered indicators of employee job satisfaction.

Table 2. Respondents' Perception on Level of Job Satisfaction

Constructs	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Autonomy	3.00	0.84	High
Skill Variety	3.32	0.65	Very High
Task Significance	3.29	0.64	Very High
Task Identity	3.26	0.66	Very High
Overall Level of Job Satisfaction	3.22	0.68	High

Note: Scale: 4.00-3.25 Very High (VH), 3.24-2.50 High (H), 2.49-1.75 Low (L), 1.00-1.74 Very Low (VL)

Healthcare organizations are social systems in which human resources are the most critical factor (Specchia et al., 2021), as job satisfaction is heavily inclined with the effectiveness of the human resources; thus, it creates a bridge between job satisfaction and job-related function realization. Studies have demonstrated the impact of job satisfaction on the motivation of workers, while the level of motivation impacts productivity, hence increasing the performance of organizations (Aziri, 2011). Hence, the high regard of hospital employees for their job satisfaction mirrored advantages to the organizational success of Medina General Hospital. Employees who are satisfied with their job-related functions may transpire in the performance of their duty, thus helping the hospital to serve its clientele by providing professional patient care and support.

In this vein, the revealed satisfaction among hospital employees in their job-related duties and responsibilities was mirrored by the constructs that underlie the operationalized instrument - autonomy, which revealed that employees were given the discretion in work-related judgments and provided a high degree of independence in the organization. This posited high regard among employees' perceptions in this construct.

Furthermore, the construct skill variety noticeably gathered the highest mean equivalent. It resulted from organizational efforts to promote the development of diversified skills in the performance of duty. The opportunity for employees to grow in the workplace and the constant skill upgrading by the organization seemed to be an effective mechanism that resulted from positive work culture. Further, the innate job description of the employees that stressed skill acquisition was also considered a factor that leads to employees' job satisfaction.

Another construct of investigation that yielded a very high level of perception was task significance. The perceived enactment between the job description and its practical application in the organization contributed to this. Also, the connection between organizational goals and objectives to job description allowed employees to be satisfied with their job. In addition, the dynamic transition of theories to practice simplified the abstract endeavor among employees in realizing organizational visions, which radiates to employees' job satisfaction.

As to task identity, hospital employees had a very high perception of this construct. The level of perceived task identity was justified by Medina General Hospital administrators'

initiatives to lessen the burden of employees on task completion. However, factors such as appropriate recognition of employees' job performance and co-workers' help in task completion circumscribed the results.

Organizations may strategize their work-arrangement strategies and employees' job evaluation assessment based on the findings being revealed in these contexts. As suggested in this investigation, a multi-perspective analysis effectively justified employees' job satisfaction. Thus, programs and implementations that promote employees' autonomy, skill variety, task significance, and task identity are vital in determining the level of job satisfaction of employees in an organization.

4.3. Perceived Work Behavior of Employees in the Organization as to Innovative and Productive Work Behavior

Table 3 divulged the perceived work behavior of employees in Medina General Hospital; verbally interpreted the overall work behavior among hospital employees as Very Evident ($M=3.38$; $SD=0.62$). Further, both constructs of the variable were perceived as Very Evident, namely, Innovative Work Behavior ($M=3.29$; $SD=0.61$) and Productive Work Behavior ($M=3.46$; $SD=0.63$).

Table 3. *Perceived Work Behavior of Employees*

Constructs	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Innovative Work Behavior	3.29	0.61	Very Evident
Productive Work Behavior	3.46	0.63	Very Evident
Overall Work Behavior	3.38	0.62	Very Evident

Note: Scale: 4.00-3.25 Very Evident (VE), 3.24-2.50 Evident (E), 2.49-1.75 Less Evident (LE), 1.00-1.74 Not Evident (NE)

Findings posited high regard among employees' perceived work behavior at the individual level. As the conceptualized indicators explain, innovativeness and productivity contribute to the employees' work behavior. As mentioned in this study, the variable work behavior can be effectively operationalized at the individual level. Thus, it should effectively inspect factors involving employees' motivation and interest.

Purwanto et al. (2020) revealed that work behavior has a very positive and significant effect on work performance. This finding revealed the causality of work behavior in understanding how employees effectively perform their duties. Therefore, it can be conclude that the empirical results herein describe the hospital employees' effectiveness in performing their duties.

Relative to the construct of Innovative Work Behavior, employees perceived their work competencies as relentlessly challenging the status quo. Hospital employees develop customized processes that encourage new ideas and motivate others to be proactive and resourceful. Further, the findings revealed that the employees' mentoring of co-employees was manifested. As disclosed in the operationalized instrument, employees inspired their co-employees to develop and implement new ideas and ways to approach work that will benefit the hospital.

As to productive work behavior, the organization's substantial use of working hours was disclosed as the contributing factor to the very evident productive work behavior in Medina General Hospital. Further, the use of motivational techniques employed by co-workers inculcated positive working attitudes towards hospital employees. Also, the appropriate resource use yielded high-quality outputs among hospital employees.

Consequently, the descriptive analysis implied that for organizations to promote positive work behavior among employees. Therefore, the administrators should inspect this variable in the individual contributing factors. Further, the socio-ecological interactions between employees and administrators should be anchored toward fostering innovativeness and productivity in the workplace.

4.4. Significant Relationship between Administrative Support and Employees' Work Behavior

The relationship between administrative support and employees' work behavior was positively correlated, $r(99) = .47, p < .001$. The result is statistically significant at $\alpha = .05$. Overall, there was a weak positive correlation between these variables. Although both variables tend to rise in response to one another, the relationship is not particularly strong and causality cannot be inferred from these correlational findings.

As cited by studies being conducted, administrative support operates at the organizational structure level and influences organizational culture (Barefield & Meyer, 2013), while work behavior was grounded on the individual factor perspective, which is subject to employee's ability, interest, and motivation (Siregar et al., 2019). Thus, the discrepancy among the levels of measurement that can justify these variables accounts for the weak correlation obtained in this investigation. Accordingly, administrative support's importance in redirecting employee energy and learning toward innovation has considerable practical significance (Riaz et al., 2018).

Managers are responsible for using individual energy due to their crucial mediating function in the creative process (Diamantidis & Chatzoglou, 2018). In this vein, organizations should recognize the importance of administrative support factors that impacting employees' work behavior. Consequently, organizations could select the most energized and opportunity-seeking employees to assign them to projects involving innovative ideas, provide support in the form of autonomy, power, information, and rewards, and promote them as an inspiration for other workers to motivate them (Riaz et al., 2018).

Table 4. Relationship between Administrative Support and Employees' Work Behavior

Variable	R-value	p-value	Strength of Association
Administrative Support and Employees' Work Behavior	0.47	$p < 0.0001$	Weak Positive Correlation

Note: Significance level is set to $p < .05$

As for organizations, the variable work organization seemed too vague. However, qualitative analysis of employees' interests and work motivation could be a breaking point

for organizational interventions. Further, the findings serve as benchmarks for investigations that inspect the mediation and causation of motivation towards work innovativeness and work behavior.

4.5. Significant Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Employees' Work Behavior

The relationship between job satisfaction and employees' work behavior was positively correlated, $r(99) = .60, p < .001$. The result is statistically significant at $\alpha = .05$. Overall, there was a moderate positive correlation between these variables.

A closer look at the revealed relationship implied the importance of job satisfaction in employees' work behavior and vice-versa. However, the findings do not provide causality towards the correlated variables; hence it cannot be justified which among these two variables caused the directionality of the relationship. In contrast, the relationship revealed considered the constructs for each variable and served as contributing indicators towards the moderate positive correlation that has been found.

The findings revealed were consistent with the disclosed studies in this parameter. Czarnota-Bojarska (2015) mentioned work behavior as a detrimental factor in an organization; he revealed that job satisfaction is significantly associated with work behavior. This was supported by Fatima et al structural equation modeling analysis (2012); there was a positive association between job satisfaction and productive work behavior. Consequently, the path analysis conducted by Mount et al. (2006) also indicated the effects of job satisfaction on employees' work behavior.

In this vein, organizational entities may derive their organizational culture and practices from the revealed relationship. It can be deduced that employees' high job satisfaction correlates with evident positive work behavior. Thus, proposed program implementations should promote employees' satisfaction in their work-related duties to foster a good working attitude.

Table 5. Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Employees' Work Behavior

Variable	R-value	p-value	Strength of Association
Job Satisfaction and Employees' Work Behavior	0.60	$p < 0.0001$	Moderate Positive Correlation

Note: Significance level is set to $p < .05$

4.6. Job Satisfaction as a Predictor of Work Behavior

A simple linear regression was used to examine job satisfaction as a predictor of employees' work behavior. Job satisfaction significantly explained employees' work behavior variance, $F(1,99) = 58.6, p < .001, R^2 = .37, \text{adjusted } R^2 = .37$. The predictor job satisfaction ($B = 0.641, SE = 0.0837, t = 7.65, p < .001$) indicated that an increase of one unit in job satisfaction was associated, on average, with a 0.64 unit increase in employees' work behavior.

The disclosed analysis further implies that apart from the positive directionality in the relationship among the independent and dependent variables, a high level of job satisfaction constitutes a very evident innovative and productive work behavior among

hospital employees. Furthermore, job satisfaction in the context of autonomy, skill variety, task significance, and task identity was a predictor of work behavior mirrored in employees' innovative and productive work behavior. Hence, this causality can serve as a basis for Medina General Hospital to improve the work behavior among hospital employees.

Hongying (2007) mentioned that understanding job satisfaction is essential in describing employees' work attitudes and behavior. Job satisfaction significantly and favorably influences job performance, thus resulting in productive work behavior (Nemteanu & Dabija, 2021). Hence, the revealed findings in this investigation were consistent with the explored parameters in this body of knowledge.

Given the consistently proven hypothetical assumptions, organizations may construct an organizational framework for promoting productive and innovative work behavior through the constructs considered in this investigation. Furthermore, the importance of promoting autonomy, skill variety, task significance, and task identity radiates in employees' work behavior. Thus, organizational administrators and policymakers may mirror the reflected findings in this study in their respective departments, offices, or organizations.

Table 6. Linear Regression Analysis between Job Satisfaction and Employees' Work Behavior

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²
1	0.610	0.372	0.365

Omnibus ANOVA Test						
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	p	
JOB SATISFACTION	6.82	1	6.818	58.6	< .001	
Residuals	11.52	9	0.116			

Model Coefficients - WORK BEHAVIOR						
Predictor	Estimate	SE	T	p	Stand. Estimate	
Intercept	1.313	0.2710	4.85	< .001		
JOB SATISFACTION	0.641	0.0837	7.65	< .001	0.610	

4.7. Summary of Results

This study aimed to provide hospital employees and administrators with feedback on administrative support, job satisfaction, and work behavior. The analytic sample used for inferential analyses consisted of 101 complete responses; earlier stages included 134 invited

and 124 returned questionnaires. Key findings: (1) administrative support was verbally interpreted as High; (2) job satisfaction was High; (3) work behavior was Very Evident; (4) weak positive correlation between administrative support and work behavior; (5) moderate positive correlation between job satisfaction and work behavior; (6) job satisfaction significantly explained variance in work behavior.

As disclosed in the data analysis made, the following were the revealed descriptive and inferential findings:

- a. administrative support given in Medina General Hospital was verbally interpreted as high;
- b. the job satisfaction of Medina General Hospital Employees was regarded as high;
- c. work behavior among hospital employees was verbally interpreted as Very Evident;
- d. there was a weak positive correlation between administrative support and employees' work behavior;
- e. job satisfaction and employees' work behavior were moderately positively correlated; and
- f. job satisfaction significantly explained the amount of variance in employees work behavior.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1. Conclusion

The findings point out that tangible and intangible support are essential in the development of a strong feeling of administrative support within an organization. Encouragement of such factors as autonomy, skill variety, task significance, and task identity play a vital role in enhancing job satisfaction in relation to employees' responsibilities and duties. Work behavior of employees is enhanced by their innovativeness and productivity in the execution of work. But, while quantifying work behavior within an organizational setting, administrative support was an ineffective linked variable because of the varying degrees of the involved factors. On the other hand, job satisfaction was directly proportional to work behavior and is an important predictor of workers' work behavior.

5.2. Recommendations

The study thus indicates that organizational administrators, department heads, and senior officials should, therefore, provide employees with what is needed both materially or immaterially. This includes course-programs offering employees improved autonomy alongside skill variety, task significance, and task identity in a corporate setting. It's a call for Human Resource directors to consider evaluating on a regular basis employee work behavior in respect to innovativeness and productivity. Future researchers should construct more localized tools for determining the relationship between administration support and work behavior, improving the hypothetical assumptions identified in this study. Finally, revisiting existing frameworks on work behavior with job satisfaction being a cardinal predictor of employee performance is suggested to organization administrators and policy makers.

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Conflict of Interest

The researcher declares that there is no conflict of interest regarding the conduct and publication of this study. No financial, personal, or institutional interest influence the outcomes, interpretations, or reporting of the findings. This research was conducted solely for academic purposes and in pursuit of contributing to educational knowledge and practice.

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